

DIRECTORY OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL JOB SITES AND REGULARLY OFFERED PAID POSITIONS

Academic Jobs Online (search “archaeology”)

<http://academicjobsonline.com/ajo/jobs>

(US and International)

Academic Jobs Wiki

https://academicjobs.fandom.com/wiki/Academic_Jobs_Wiki

(Canada, US, and International)

AcademicWork.ca (Filter by: Archaeology)

www.academicwork.ca

(Canada)

Academic Positions (Filter by: Archaeology)

<http://academicpositions.com>

(Europe, including Turkey)

Alexander von Humboldt Foundation

<https://www.humboldt-foundation.de/>

(Germany)

Anthropology Careers & Employment (Discipline: Archaeology)

<https://careercenter.americananthro.org/jobs/>

(US and International)

American Institute of Archaeology

<https://www.archaeological.org/programs/professionals/careers/>

(US and Canada)

American Research Center in Egypt

<https://arce.org/fellowships-landing/>

(International)

Archeonet BE

<https://www.facebook.com/archeonet/>

(Belgium)

Archeovacatures NL

<http://www.archeovacatures.nl/vacatures/>

(Netherlands)

ACOR – Fellowships

<http://www.acorjordan.org/neh-fellowship/>

(Jordan)

American Institute of Pakistan Studies – Fellowships

<https://pakistanstudies-aips.org/fellowship>

(International)

American Schools of Oriental Research (ASOR) – Fellowships

<http://www.asor.org/fellowships/>

(International)

BAJR

<https://www.bajr.org/find-a-job/>

(UK and International)

Banting Postdoctoral Fellowships

<http://banting.fellowships-bourses.gc.ca/en/home-accueil.html>

(Canada)

British Institute at Ankara

<https://biaa.ac.uk/grants-opportunities/>

(UK and International)

British Institute for the Study of Iraq

<https://www.bisi.ac.uk/grants-scholarships/>

(UK and International)

The British Museum

<https://bmrecruit.ciphr-irecruit.com/applicants/vacancy>

(UK)

British School of Rome – various funded fellowships (click on “Awards” then choose a theme)

<https://bsr.ac.uk/>

(Rome)

CADW

<https://cadw.gov.wales/about-us/careers/work-cadw>

(UK)

Center for Environmental Management of Military Lands

<https://cemml.colostate.edu/careers/>

(US)

Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) (search “archéologie”)

<https://emploi.cnrs.fr/>

(France)

Chartered Institute for Archaeologists (CIFA)

<https://www.archaeologists.net/careers>

(UK)

Chronicle (search “archaeology”)

<https://jobs.chronicle.com/>

(US and International)

Council of American Research Centers

<https://www.caorc.org/fellowships>

(International)

Columbia Global Centers Fellowships

<https://globalcenters.columbia.edu/amman/what-we-do/fellowship-programs>

(International)

Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst (DAAD)

<https://www2.daad.de/deutschland/stipendium/datenbank/de/21148-stipendiendatenbank/>

(Germany and International)

Deutsches Archäologisches Institut (DAI)

<https://www.dainst.org/en/career/early-scientific-career>

<https://www.dainst.org/karriere/dai-als-arbeitgeber>

(Germany and International)

DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft / German Research Foundation) – Includes postdoctoral positions: “Nach der Promotion” / “Following Completion of Doctorates”

<https://www.dfg.de/de/foerderung/foerdermoeglichkeiten/programme>

<https://www.dfg.de/en/research-funding/funding-opportunities/programmes>

(Germany)

Dumbarton Oaks Fellowships

<https://www.doaks.org/research/fellowships-and-awards>

(US)

Earthworks

<https://www.earthworks-jobs.com/>

(International)

EURAXESS – European Commission (search “archaeology”)

<https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs>

(Europe and International)

The Explorer’s Club Student Grants (includes early career post-doctoral funding)

<https://www.explorers.org/grants/>

(International)

Guardian Jobs, Museums & Galleries Jobs

<https://jobs.theguardian.com/jobs/arts-and-heritage/>

(UK)

H-Net Jobs

<https://networks.h-net.org/jobs/browse>

(International)

Heritage Alliance News and Sector Vacancies

<https://www.theheritagealliance.org.uk/news-and-events/news/#vacancies>

(UK)

Heritage Council

<https://www.heritagecouncil.ie/news/jobs>

(Ireland)

Higher Education Recruitment Consortium (HERC) (search “archaeology”)

<http://main.hercjobs.org/jobs>

(US)

HigherEd Jobs (search “archaeology” and “archeology”)

<http://www.higheredjobs.com/>

(US)

Historic England

<https://historicengland.org.uk/about/jobs/>

(UK)

Historic Scotland

<https://www.historicenvironment.scot/about-us/work-with-us/current-vacancies/>

(UK)

ICCROM – Jobs, Fellowships, Internships

<https://www.iccrom.org/get-involved/opportunities>

(International)

Inside Higher Ed (search “archaeology” and “archeology”)

<http://careers.insidehighered.com>

(US and International)

Institute for the Study of the Ancient World (ISAW) – Visiting Scholars

<https://isaw.nyu.edu/visiting-scholars>

(US)

International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS) – Jobs and Internships

<https://www.icomos.org/work-with-icomos/>

(International)

Jobs.ac.uk (search “archaeology”)

<http://www.jobs.ac.uk/>

(UK)

Le Louvre

<http://www.louvre.fr/offres-d-emploi>

(France)

The Metropolitan Museum of New York – Internships and Fellowships

<https://www.metmuseum.org/about-the-met/internships>

(US)

The Metropolitan Museum of New York – Career Opportunities

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/the-metropolitan-museum-of-art/jobs/>

(US)

Museum Association Jobs

<https://www.museumsassociation.org/careers/find-a-job/>

(UK)

Museum Jobs.com

<http://www.museumjobs.com/>

(UK and International)

National Museum Director’s Council

<http://www.nationalmuseums.org.uk/jobs/>

(UK)

The National Trust

<https://www.nationaltrustjobs.org.uk/jobs/>

(UK)

Nature (search “archaeology”)

<https://www.nature.com/naturecareers>

(International)

Parks Canada

<https://www.pc.gc.ca/en/agence-agency/emplois-jobs>

(Canada)

PreserveNet

<https://preservenet.org/>

(US and International)

ResearchGate (search “archaeology” and “archeology”)

<https://www.researchgate.net/jobs?page=1®ions=>

(International)

The Register of Professional Archaeologists (RPA)

<https://rpanet.org/RPA-Jobs>

(US)

Seek

<https://au.seek.com/archaeology-jobs>

(Australia)

<https://nz.seek.com/archaeology-jobs>

(New Zealand)

Shovelbums

<https://groups.io/g/ShovelBums/messages>

(US and Canada)

Smithsonian

<https://www.si.edu/ohr/jobs>

(US)

Society for American Anthropology

<https://careers.saa.org/jobs/>

(US and International)

Times Higher Education (search “archaeology”)

<https://www.timeshighereducation.com/unijobs/>

(International)

Underwater Archaeology and Maritime History Jobs

<https://underwaterarchaeologyjobs.com/>

(International)

UNESCO – Careers and Fellowships

<https://www.unesco.org/en/careers>

<https://www.unesco.org/en/fellowships>

(International)

University Affairs (search “archaeology”)

<https://www.universityaffairs.ca/search-job/>

(Canada)

Uni Roles

<https://uniroles.com.au/>

(Australia)

University of Chicago Institute for the Study of Ancient Cultures Postdoctoral Fellowship Program

<https://isac.uchicago.edu/research/postdoctoral-fellow-program>

(US)

USA Jobs (search for both “archaeology” and “archeology”)

<http://www.usajobs.gov/>

(US)

Volkswagen Stiftung

<https://www.volkswagenstiftung.de/en>

(Germany and International)

World Monuments Fund

<https://www.wmf.org/jobs>

(International)